

Church of the Holy Apostles

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Entry tags: Christianity, Christian, Greece, Religious Group, Christian Orthodox, Classical Indo-European, Indo-European, Thessaloniki, Language, Orthodoxy, Religious Place, Graeco-Phrygian, Orthodoxy, Greek

The Palaeologan church dedicated to the Holy Apostles in the city of Thessaloniki, Greece, dates around the late 13th and early 14th century. It is located in the western part of the historic centre of Thessaloniki, near the west wall and the Litaia Gate, which does not exist any longer. It is likely that the church was the *katholikon* (the main church) of an unidentified monastery and that it was likely dedicated to the Mother of God, probably that of Theotokos Gorgoepikoos. This hypothesis was based on the depiction of the second founder, Paul, who was a former disciple of Patriarch Niphon I and also the abbot of the monastery, depicted praying before the enthroned Virgin. The scene is located above the entrance leading from the narthex to the nave, along with scenes from the Life of the Virgin in the ambulatory. Surviving structures in the vicinity of the church include part of the once imposing tower-shaped portal with a large barrel-vaulted passage to the south-west, and a large cistern to the north-west, the size of which attests to the large number of monks living there, as well as the monastery's wealth. According to tradition, the church has taken its current name from the popular belief that it had a twelve-domed roof symbolizing the Apostles. The *katholikon* was constructed between 1310 and 1314 by Patriarch Niphon I, as attested by the inscription on the marble lintel above the main entrance; the monograms on the capitals of the west facade and the monograms on bricks. A painted inscription over the entrance to the naos mentions also Patriarch Niphon and his disciple Paul, as founders of the monastery. Based on dendrochronological data, the monument was dated to or just after 1329. It was originally suggested that the naos and the narthex are earlier and that Niphon added later the ambulatory and restored it. Current research suggests that the whole building dates to the same period and that it may have been left unfinished when Niphon was expelled from office in 1314, and that it was completed later. The Holy Apostles is a cross-in-square church with a tripartite sanctuary and a narthex. The ambulatory consists of longitudinal *parekklesia* connecting with the outer narthex (*exonarthex*) to the west. The main dome is surrounded by four smaller domes in the ambulatory, with two domes on its eastern ends and a second pair of domes flanking the narthex. The domed chapels on the eastern ends communicate directly with the tripartite sanctuary. Between the domes of each *parekklesion* are two bays with a single groin vault and a single domical vault. The southern chapel originally had a door, which was at a point walled up. The church has a U-shaped ambulatory enveloping the naos and the narthex. The exterior is lavishly decorated with ornamental brickwork, typical of Palaeologan monuments. The interior is decorated with mosaics sponsored by Patriarch Niphon. The Pantocrator is depicted in the central dome, surrounded by ten Prophets. The four Evangelists are depicted alongside scenes from the Dodekaorton: Nativity, Transfiguration, Entry into Jerusalem, Resurrection, Crucifixion and Assumption. With the mosaics of the Monasteries of Chora and Pammakaristos in Constantinople, those of the Holy Apostles of Thessaloniki are the latest examples of similar decoration in Byzantium, considered among the finest of Palaeologan art. Frescoes of equally high quality were painted in the lower parts of the nave, the narthex, the peristyle and the north chapel, dedicated to Saint John the Baptist, bearing scenes from the Old and New Testaments, and subjects either inspired by hymnography or of symbolic nature. The wall paintings date to the late 1410s, and have been linked to the abbacy of Paul, the second founder of the Monastery. Perhaps around 1455 or 1520 the Ottomans converted the church into a mosque. A minaret was added to the south-west corner of the monument and a wooden porch was erected to its northern and western sides. It became a church in 1912 when Greeks took control of the city. Restoration took place between 1926-1928 and 1940-1942, which included the removal of the Ottoman plasters covering the interior decoration. Consolidation works were carried out after the earthquake of 1978. In 2002 the mosaics were cleaned. The monument was inscribed in the UNESCO List of World Heritage

Sites.

Date Range: 1310 CE - 2024 CE

Region: Church of the Holy Apostles, Thessaloniki

Region tags: Thessaloniki, Greece

The Church of the Holy Apostles is located in the western part of the historic centre of Thessaloniki.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Nikonanos, N. Οι Άγιοι Απόστολοι Θεσσαλονίκης. Thessaloniki, 1986.
- Source 2: Rautman, M. L. . The Church of the Holy Apostles in Thessaloniki: A Study in Early Palaeologan Architecture. Unpublished Ph.D. Dissertation. Bloomington, 1984.
- Source 3: Kuniholm, P. I., and C. L. Striker. "Dendrochronology and the Architectural History of the Church of the Holy Apostles in Thessaloniki." Architectura: Zeitschrift Für Geschichte Der Baukunst 20 (1990).

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: http://odysseus.culture.gr/h/2/gh251.jsp?obj_id=1682
- Source 1 Description: Hellenic Ministry of Culture and Sports
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.thebyzantinelegacy.com/apostoloi-thessaloniki>
- Source 2 Description: Detailed description of the monument and photographs
- Source 3 URL: <https://youtu.be/AFemGA3edC4>
- Source 3 Description: Short video about the monument

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– No

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Water source

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

– Water feature

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– No

Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

A single structure

– No

One single feature

– Other [specify]: The church is located within the urban area of the city of Thessaloniki

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Notes: Surviving structures in the vicinity of the church include part of the once imposing tower-shaped portal with a large barrel-vaulted passage to the south-west, and a large cistern to the north-west. We are not really aware when they were built.

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Notes: Surviving structures in the vicinity of the church include part of the once imposing tower-shaped portal with a large barrel-vaulted passage to the south-west, and a large cistern to the north-west. We are not really aware when they were built.

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

Notes: The church was the katholikon of a monastery

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

Notes: It was originally suggested that the naos and the narthex are earlier and that

Patriarch Niphon I added later the ambulatory and restored it. Current research suggests that the whole building dates to the same period and that it may have been left unfinished when Niphon was expelled from office in 1314, and that it was completed later.

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Notes: It was not reconstructed but it was completed in two phases.

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– No

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– No

Notes: The church was founded by Patriarch Niphon I.

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

↳ Groups:

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Notes: It was sponsored by Patriarch Niphon I and later by his student Paul.

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: It is not clear for which reasons Patriarch Niphon I founded the monastery.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Sand

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Clay

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Wood
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Grass
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Stone
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Other
– Other [specify]: Glass tesserae for the mosaics, pigments and binders for the frescoes.

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Pigments, binders and glass tesserae for the mosaics.

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

Notes: Ceramoplastic decoration and other decorative elements such as arched windows.

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Notes: Iconostasis and icons, proskynetaria for posing the icons.

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Jesus Christ, the Son of God.

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Angels.

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Saints, Prophets, Evangelists, Jesus Christ, Virgin Mary and Paul the second founder of the monastery. Anonymous humans are also depicted in the narrative

scenes.

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

Notes: They are depicted in the narrative scenes.

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– No

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– Yes

Notes: Icons

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Type

– 'True' fresco

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– Yes

Notes: Saints, Evangelists, Prophets, Jesus Christ and the Mother of God, angels.

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

Notes: Scenes from the Life of Christ and from the Life of Virgin Mary.

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– Yes

↳ Mosaics representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– Yes

Notes: Jesus Christ and Virgin Mary, Prophets and Evangelists.

↳ Mosaics representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Mosaics representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

Notes: Scenes from the Life of Christ and Virgin Mary.

↳ Abstract mosaics:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: Only fragments from the original mosaic decoration are preserved.

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– No

Notes: Inscriptions in Orthodox churches are always providing information regarding

the person and the scene depicted. They are never ornamental.

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

Notes: Inscriptions in Orthodox churches are always providing information regarding the person and the scene depicted. They are never ornamental.

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: There is an inscription on the marble lintel above the main entrance mentioning the founder of the monastery. His monograms are found also on the capitals of the west facade and on bricks.

↳ Other type of decoration:

– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– Yes

Notes: Byzantine style.

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: Angels

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

Notes: Cross, Anastasis.

↳ Humans

– Yes

Notes: Saints, Evangelists, Virgin Mary, Jesus Christ, Prophets, Paul the second founder of the church, and many other persons depicted in the narrative scenes of the Dodekaorton and the Life of the Virgin.

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Yes

Notes: The scenes from the life of Christ, such as the Anastasis, the Transfiguration etc.

↳ Human narratives

– Yes

Notes: Scenes from the life of Virgin Mary and Christ.

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: Genealogy of Christ (Tree of Jesse)

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Notes: People do come to pray though at the church, which is sort of a kind of communication with God.

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– No

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: Divine liturgy and other services are performed.

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

–specify: It is not possible to know

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

–specify: At least once a week (Divine Liturgy).

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Yes

Notes: The Orthodox ritual is followed.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Yes

Notes: The Orthodox ritual is followed.

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– No

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– No

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

Notes: Offerings can be anything, from very simple things like bread, wine, olive oil and they can be also very valuable objects.

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

Notes: Offerings can be anything, from very simple things like bread, wine, olive oil and they can be also very valuable objects.

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Offerings for Christian Orthodox churches and monasteries can be anything and their value can vary significantly.

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

Notes: It is required for the preservation of the monument, which is also a functioning one.

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– No

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

Notes: They are required for the preservation of the monument.

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Yes

Notes: Maintenance can be performed by the staff of the church and the priests and also by the archaeologists and other specialists called to contribute to the monument's restoration.

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Many specialists and researchers are interested in the monument and are collaboratively working for its preservation.

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Notes: There are however always pilgrims in the sense that people come to pray and venerate the icons of the church.

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– No

↳ Present part time

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: Male

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

Notes: The priests that perform the sacred rituals at the church follow the hierarchy of the Orthodox church.

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Notes: It does not, however, it was a functioning monastery in the past.

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: The Ephorate of Byzantine Antiquities of the Ministry of Culture and Sports and the Bishopric of Thessaloniki are in charge of the monument

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

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